

ANALYSIS OF ACUTE ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) remains one of the most urgent problems in pediatric surgery due to its high incidence, diagnostic complexity, and risk of recurrence. This study analyzes the etiology, diagnostic accuracy, and treatment outcomes of 231 pediatric patients with adhesive intestinal obstruction treated between 2018 and 2023. Early adhesive intestinal obstruction (EAIO) was observed mainly after destructive appendicitis and appendicular peritonitis, accounting for 49.3% of cases. Diagnostic comparison showed that ultrasonography demonstrated higher sensitivity (94.6%) and specificity (91.1%) compared with conventional radiography (85.7% and 90.0%, respectively). Laparoscopy proved to be a highly accurate and minimally invasive method for early diagnosis and surgical management, providing 100% diagnostic accuracy and 87% informativeness. Conservative therapy was effective in 57.6% of cases, while 42.4% of patients required emergency surgery. The integration of ultrasound monitoring and diagnostic laparoscopy ensured earlier detection, reduced complications, and improved clinical outcomes. The findings emphasize the importance of combined imaging methods and the use of minimally invasive approaches in managing both early and late adhesive intestinal obstruction in children.

Introduction. According to domestic and foreign researchers, the incidence of abdominal adhesions can reach up to 93% [11]. The problem of peritoneal fibrosis remains relevant and requires further scientific investigation. According to N.F. Ray (1994) [13], more than 300,000 operations for adhesive intestinal obstruction are performed annually in the United States, resulting in healthcare expenditures of about 1.3 billion dollars. Adhesive intestinal obstruction accounts for 60–90% of all cases of intestinal obstruction. It should also be noted that 90–94% of cases are associated with

acute small bowel obstruction (ASBO), which has a more severe course and a less favorable prognosis for patients [4,10]. According to various sources, postoperative mortality in cases of complicated ASBO can reach 10–15% [2,8,12].

Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) in children accounts for up to 75% of all types of mechanical intestinal obstruction. Almost 60% of emergency relaparotomies in children are performed due to this pathology [3,5]. The increase in AAIO cases is associated with the growing number and volume of abdominal surgical interventions, often due to overdiagnosis of acute surgical diseases. A significant factor is the indication for surgical treatment of early adhesive intestinal obstruction (EAIO), the diagnosis of which may be difficult. There also remains a serious problem of preventing adhesive processes in the early postoperative period, which may lead to unnecessary or delayed operations [3,10].

According to many researchers, the development of late adhesive intestinal obstruction (LAIO) is often associated with inadequate sanitation of the abdominal cavity and the high traumatic nature of laparotomy [1,9]. An important factor is the individual predisposition of patients to adhesion formation. In recent years, biochemical mechanisms contributing to this process have been actively studied [6,8]. However, none of the currently known preventive methods can completely prevent the development of adhesion formation.

Diagnostic Approaches. During radiographic examination of the abdominal organs performed in the supine and upright positions, an increase in the intestinal lumen due to gas or fluid accumulation can be detected, which allows determination of their level [4,10]. However, the diagnostic accuracy of conventional radiography remains limited [11].

For the diagnosis of adhesive intestinal obstruction (AIO), abdominal computed tomography (CT) with oral contrast agents is useful [7]. These contrast materials are considered safer in terms of peritonitis risk compared to barium [13]. Studies using water-soluble contrast agents allow assessment of the feasibility of conservative treatment in such patients [11]. Some researchers claim that the use of such contrast agents is effective for detecting complete forms of AIO and determining the appropriateness of non-operative management.

CT can reveal the presence of extraluminal air, bowel wall thickening, mesenteric edema, mesenteric venous stasis, as well as intraluminal gas accumulation and free fluid in the abdominal cavity [1,7].

Treatment Considerations. Ineffectiveness of conservative therapy in cases of late adhesive intestinal obstruction (LAIO) often necessitates laparoscopic adhesiolysis. This method is considered preferable because operations performed through a more traumatic midline laparotomy often lead to recurrence of the disease [2,7,12]. Timely conversion from conservative to surgical treatment can improve patient outcomes.

Objective of the Study. The aim of our study was to analyze the treatment outcomes in children with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) and to compare the frequency of late adhesive intestinal obstruction (LAIO) after surgeries performed via laparotomy and laparoscopy.

Materials and Methods. From 2018 to 2023, 231 patients aged 7 months to 18 years with adhesive intestinal obstruction (AIO) were treated at the Fergana Branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care and at a multidisciplinary hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among them, 93 were girls (40.7%) and 138 were boys (59.3%). All patients exhibited characteristic symptoms, including abdominal pain and vomiting; their histories revealed previous abdominal surgeries for various diseases.

In 114 patients, acute intestinal obstruction occurred after appendectomy performed via the Volkovich–Dyakov incision. A complicated course of acute appendicitis with peritonitis had been documented. Eleven children underwent surgery via a midline laparotomy.

Three patients had previously undergone midline laparotomy for complications related to Meckel's diverticulum and unresolved intussusception, which required small bowel resection. In eight cases, midline laparotomy was performed for closed abdominal trauma, including ruptures of the liver and spleen and internal bleeding. Twenty children underwent surgical treatment for congenital gastrointestinal malformations during the neonatal period. In seven children, adhesive processes developed after elective surgeries.

In 56 patients, recurrent adhesive intestinal obstruction (RAIO) occurred within 2–30 days after a previous laparotomy performed via a midline incision. In 175 patients, late adhesive intestinal obstruction (LAIO) developed 1 month to 15 years after initial treatment.

The clinical picture was characterized by typical abdominal pain in 98.2% of patients. Repeated vomiting was observed in 96.2%, abdominal distension in 96.9%, and asymmetry of the abdomen in 6.5% of cases.

All children diagnosed with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) received conservative treatment according to the established clinical protocol. This included gastric decompression and lavage, stimulation of intestinal peristalsis with subcutaneous neostigmine at age-appropriate doses three times every 30 minutes, and cleansing enemas. If no positive effect was observed within 2 hours, bilateral paranephric block with 0.25% novocaine solution was administered at an appropriate dose. The effectiveness of conservative therapy was evaluated based on the passage of a barium suspension through the gastrointestinal tract. In the absence of improvement, surgical intervention was performed.

Results and Discussion. An analysis of the surgical diseases that required primary operations showed that early adhesive intestinal obstruction was most frequently observed in patients operated on for destructive appendicitis and appendicular peritonitis — in 114 cases (49.3%).

Clinical examination was performed using a standard methodology, during which the dynamics of the general condition and well-being of the patients were evaluated. Special attention was paid to the nature of pain, restoration of gastrointestinal tract function, presence of vomiting, volume of stagnant gastric content, intestinal peristalsis, and the passage of gases and stool. The dynamics of the pain syndrome in the postoperative period were assessed in both the main and control groups.

In our opinion, timely detection of early adhesive intestinal obstruction is achieved through a detailed analysis of the postoperative course, as well as based on the results of radiological, ultrasonographic, and endoscopic examinations.

An overview abdominal X-ray was performed for all patients with suspected adhesive intestinal obstruction. Dynamic abdominal sonography plays a key role in the diagnosis of early adhesive intestinal obstruction. The non-invasive nature of this method and the possibility of repeated examinations allow its use for dynamic monitoring of the course of the local pathological process. Ultrasound examinations were performed for all patients in both groups.

During the analysis, we identified several echographic criteria, among which the most consistent was the visualization of the afferent loop of the intestinal tube filled with fluid content.

In the study of ultrasound semiotics of the abdominal organs, the following signs were identified: decreased intestinal peristalsis, pendulum-like movement of the contents within the intestinal lumen, uneven gas distribution, as well as the presence of free fluid, pus, abscesses, masses, and infiltrates that impede the passage of intestinal contents. Table 1 presents the data on the diagnostic efficiency of overview abdominal radiography and ultrasonography.

Table 1

Diagnostic Efficiency (%) of Overview Abdominal Radiography and Ultrasonography

Diagnostic Parameter	Type of Examination		Reliability / Significance (p)
Sensitivity	Radiography 85.7%	Ultrasonography 94.6%	p < 0.05
Specificity	Radiography 90.0%	Ultrasonography 91.1%	p < 0.05

Results and Discussion. A comparative analysis of the diagnostic efficiency of the two methods in detecting early adhesive intestinal obstruction (EAIO) did not reveal statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Nevertheless, their combined use appears advisable, as it may increase the overall diagnostic informativeness.

An analysis of the causes and clinical features of EAIO in 56 children, based on postoperative radiological and ultrasound examinations of the abdominal cavity, made it possible to identify a complex of symptoms indicating an increased risk of early adhesive intestinal obstruction:

- Lack of positive dynamics in the patient's condition by the 2nd–3rd day after the primary surgery, which was performed more than 24 hours after the onset of the disease;
- By the 2nd–3rd postoperative day, either an increase or the absence of reduction in the volume of gastric residual contents;

- Persistence of signs of intoxication, hyperthermia, and intestinal paresis on the 2nd–3rd postoperative day;
- Persistence of abdominal pain and mild peritoneal irritation symptoms on the 2nd–3rd postoperative day;
- Detection of ultrasound features indicative of mechanical intestinal obstruction.

The combination of these symptoms, the clinical picture, and instrumental study results provides a rationale for performing diagnostic laparoscopy during the postoperative period. This approach facilitates early and accurate diagnosis, allows for objective assessment of the extent and nature of adhesive processes in the abdominal cavity, and enables timely surgical intervention when required.

Adhesive intestinal obstruction was successfully managed conservatively in 133 patients, including three cases where paranephric blockade was applied. Emergency surgical intervention was required in 98 children (42.4%) due to the ineffectiveness of conservative treatment.

Among these, early adhesive intestinal obstruction (EAIO) was diagnosed in 56 cases, of which 29 patients had the adhesive–paretic form complicating the postoperative course after generalized appendicular peritonitis. Laparoscopy proved effective in 5 cases, while 22 children required open surgery via a median laparotomy. In five patients, treatment included laparoscopy, adhesiolysis, and restoration of intestinal patency. Laparotomy with adhesiolysis was performed in 22 patients, and in one case, intestinal resection was necessary due to bowel wall necrosis.

Seventy-one (71) patients underwent surgery for late adhesive intestinal obstruction (LAIO). In 24 children, laparoscopic adhesiolysis was performed; however, in 8 of these cases, intestinal patency could not be restored laparoscopically, requiring conversion to open laparotomy for adhesiolysis. Forty-seven (47) patients underwent median laparotomy from the outset for adhesiolysis and restoration of intestinal passage. In 13 cases, due to delayed hospital admission and intestinal necrosis caused by strangulation, laparotomy with bowel resection was required.

In the postoperative period, patients received comprehensive intensive therapy.

Clinical treatment efficacy was evaluated based on the following criteria: the patient's general condition and well-being, the volume and rate of reduction of gastric residual contents, the time required for the restoration of spontaneous defecation, and the duration of stay in the intensive care unit and hospital. The volume of gastric residual content was identified as a key indicator of intestinal functional recovery.

Conclusions. Acute appendicitis with complications and the subsequent surgical interventions were the leading causes of early and late adhesive intestinal obstruction, observed in 49.3% of cases.

The use of modern approaches to early diagnosis and minimally invasive treatment of adhesive–paretic intestinal obstruction at early stages has led to significant improvement in therapeutic outcomes. Ultrasound examination remains a non-invasive and highly informative diagnostic method for early adhesive intestinal obstruction in children, with a diagnostic value of 94.6% and an informativeness of 91.1%.

The most accurate diagnostic method for early adhesive intestinal obstruction in

children is diagnostic laparoscopy, which demonstrates 100% diagnostic value and 87% informativeness.

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